

EMBOSSED KHIVA PILLARS**Ismailov Tokhir**

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The Jome Mosque of Khiva, which has more than a thousand years of history, is distinguished by its unique construction and size. The building is located between the road connecting the East and west gates of Ichon-Qal'a, and is built with a one-story flat roof. The mosque has entrance doors on all four sides, and its main door is a two-humped gate pointing north. Arabic to the of this gate, in the letter of suls the following Hadith is written,

The best of Deeds is the Savior,

The good of the property is sufficient.

The mosque is 4.5 meters high, with a 213-column interior area of 55x45 meters. The old and most beautiful examples of woodcarving art still function in this mosque, where about five thousand people can pray. While some of these columns were worked in the 13th and 15th centuries, the vast majority date to the 19th and 20th centuries. The 12 oldest of these pillars, preserved to this day, were worked in the 10th-12th centuries. The large number of columns, their correction in a thousand years, makes it possible to evaluate the work of Khorezm woodcarving Masters. If attention is paid, the variety of patterns on the column and their beauty from each other attracts the attention of a person. The most notable aspect is that as the pillars become more ancient, the beauty in them goes back. This thing lies in the depth, fineness of the patterns. In the 10th-11th century, historical records were written on The worked columns, while from the 15th-16th centuries it is known that Hadith began to be written on them. Arab tourists who came to Khorezm in the 10th century of Al-Istakhri¹ and Al-Mukaddasiys² it is testified that the mosque was built in the 9th-10th centuries. The holy work "Ahsan at taqosim fi Ma'riqat al - Aqolim (the best distribution for the study of the countries)" gives such information about Khiva: - "Khiva is a city of azim on the edge of the desert, and is on the side of the canal that is released from the river. It has a large Jome mosque". The historical references to Khiva in this work are also very valuable, see what else is noted in it: "grapes, lots of raisins, cinnamon, sesame, road cloth clothes, carpets, elegant fragments, locks,

¹ [Истахри](#) // [Энциклопедический словарь Брокгауза и Ефрона](#) : в 86 т. (82 т. и 4 доп.). — СПб., 1890—1907

² Rahman, Mushtaqur (2008). "Al-Muqaddasi". *Encyclopaedia of the History of Science, Technology, and Medicine in Non-Western Cultures*. p. 145. [doi:10.1007/978-1-4020-4425-0_8963](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4425-0_8963). ISBN 978-1-4020-4559-2.

colorful clothes, arrows that only strong people can use, special cheese, straws, fish are grown there. Ships will be built there"³.

According to the long-standing khivans, the Kohna mosque has become obsolete, and the present mosque was built in its place two hundred years ago, greatly expanding according to the same plan. According to historical records the mosque was rebuilt in 1788 by Abdurahimboy, the eldest son of Abdurakhman Mekhtar. Abdurakhman Mekhtar was buried in a small mausoleum on the day-out side of the mosque.

In the middle of the mosque merciful is a pomegranate tree with colored dyes and its fruits ripening on its branches. The painting is attributed to the ancient pre-Islamic belief of the khwarezmians that the image of Anachita holding a pomegranate in its hand is a fertility deity. When Islam entered, such dates and idols were lost. After that, the pomegranate flower or its fruit began to be made in some places. Engraved letters were finished on marble stones placed on the two adjacent walls of the mosque, with one of the letters listing the foundation of the mosque's property and funds, and the other listing references to the history of the mosque. It states that by the Edict of Wazir Abdurahman in 1203 Ah (1788) There are reports of waqf lands being allocated to the mosque in the villages of Kuyuk tom (now a village in Qushkupir district) and Bekabad and the expenditure of income on donations as well as the necessity of the mosque.

After entering through the door of the mosque, there is a debate about the tree of a pillar standing in the second row. Because its pattern is similar to the Indian style, Pahlavon was gifted to Mahmud from an Indian king and is believed to be made from a hawthorn tree. Indeed, the patterns in it are not found in any other column or door. In particular, the image of a seated Buddha and a standing Brahma hidden inside patterns supposedly prove these hypotheses. It is said that another pillar brought from India was touched by The Hand of Khizr, the Lord, so that the Jami of the pillars of the mosque comes out differently every time it is counted, that is, it is counted wrongly. It will have to be counted several times, by the end it will be mistaken. Most of the works on the mosque also feature this, with some books listing issues 212, 211, 200.

Depending on the position of the pillars of the mosque, the number of columns in the direction from North to South is 13, and the number of columns in the direction from East to West is 17. Due to the curved construction of the mosque's Western Wall (trapezoidal), 5 columns were laid low on the south side of the last row. There is also one in front of the mehrb, not one in the special

³ Ahmedov B. Lessons from history. T.-1994. 331 p.

areas of the roof between the mosque where the two are left open. These areas left open served the exchange of air in the mosque. According to some elderly people, the top of mosques, originally the home of God, is open, and this open space sucks to be close to God in heaven.

In the middle of the building stands a marble cauldron, the top of which is suppressed by a white dome. The cauldron can be viewed through windows placed on all four sides. Two jugs on the qibla side of the cauldron were also buried in the soup as if it were a cauldron. During the Khanate period, when the mosque was operating, there was always hot water inside this cauldron. The water in this cauldron, which was not lit anywhere, received heat from a single candle underground. The community prayer on Fridays was also attended by Khan, the Khutba was required to be read with the name of the ruler and a sermon was read after the prayer. The preachers were so adept at their work that the subject being read took place in the heart of the audience. The tower, which was built by attaching the mosque to the entrance door, was 42 meters high, from which muazzin recited five prayers a day and called the people to prayer.

Birnecha myths and legends are woven about the tower. One of them says that the old tower of the mosque collapsed. It turns out that there are no funds for the restoration of a new one. The imam then took an imperceptible portion of the Daily Meal and began to gather at one end. After some opportunity, he called the Masters and ordered the funds raised to build such a tower-so that the money would not increase, and the tower would be fully finished. The Masters finished the working Tower with pleasure. The imam called everyone and thanked the Masters, saying: "Look, if I do not restrain my ego, I will eat this tower".

This is the father poet Fozil Zohid⁴ described thus:

A dirham collected from his daily rations,
As long as there is the man who built the tower.
One day, looking at the tower, debdi he,
O thou that I may give thy soul,.

Another tradition says that when the tower is finished, mehtar tells Khan that he built it from his honest money, not using a single coin for him from the Treasury. If forbidden money is added to it, it says that it will fall on me before, and it will also build its tomb near the tower. Indeed, on the eastern side of the Jome

⁴ <https://baxtiyor.uz/fozil-zohid-haqida-ma-lumot/>

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mosque is the Tomb of Abdurahman mehtar. The mosque was opened for tourists to watch from 1983.

References:

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